

Prevalence of Programming Misconceptions in Primary School Students

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Abstract

This study investigates the prevalence of programming misconceptions among primary school students using the Programming Misconception Assessment Tool (ProMAT). The ProMAT was designed to measure programming misconceptions in two educational programming environments: Scratch and xLogo. We analyzed data from 366 Grade 5 and 6 children in German-speaking Switzerland to identify common misconceptions about sequences, loops, conditionals and to find out if they believed that there is a hidden mind in the programming environment that has intelligent interpretive powers (the so-called superbug misconception). In addition, we compared response patterns across the two programming environments. We found two misconceptions related to loops to be most common in Scratch, namely the belief that loops produce the exact same output in every iteration and that each command inside a loop is repeated separately. For xLogo, the most common misconception was from the sequences category, namely relating to the order of subprogram execution. Furthermore, variations of the superbug misconception were more prevalent among xLogo than among Scratch learners. We discuss how our results compare and add to the outcomes of earlier work, including the seminal study by Swidan and colleagues (2018). Finally, we explain how programming-environment-specific features might influence the formation or prevention of misconceptions in primary school students.

CCS Concepts

• **Social and professional topics** → **K-12 education; Student assessment.**

Keywords

Computer Science Education, K-12, Programming Misconceptions, Assessment

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1 Introduction

Learning to program has become a goal in primary school curricula across many countries, such as Switzerland [2], Germany [20], and the UK [21]. To support this endeavor, we aim to investigate possible misconceptions students might form when learning to program. For the purpose of our study we use the broad definition of programming misconceptions by Sorva [28] who described programming misconceptions as “understandings that are deficient or inadequate for many practical programming contexts”. Research in other fields, such as physics [e.g. 6, 26], or mathematics [e.g. 9, 15] has shown that a better understanding of misconceptions learners may hold, leads to better teaching and development of teaching materials.

Until now programming misconception research has mainly focused on students in introductory courses at the university level. For a literature overview see Qian and Lehman [24]. However, with the growth of programming education for primary school students, researchers also have started to investigate misconceptions in younger learners [7, 19, 29]. Children have different learning requirements, due to differences in their cognitive skills and the programming environments in which they are learning to code. It is therefore important to get a systematic overview of the different misconceptions they form, their prevalence and how they reveal themselves in commonly used educational programming environments.

To investigate misconceptions at the primary school level, we developed a multiple-choice assessment tool called the Programming Misconceptions Assessment Tool (ProMAT). For more details on the tool development see Hartmann et al. [10].

This assessment consists of 20 multiple choice items. In each item the children are asked to examine a short program written in either Scratch or xLogo and to pick one of the four answer options that correctly describes what the program is doing. For every item, we formulated distractor answers mapping onto specific misconceptions identified from the literature. The children’s answers allow us to make assumptions about the programming misconceptions they might have. For the current study, we recruited classes that had had programming lessons in school. As programming is introduced in German-speaking Switzerland as a subject in Grade 5, all included classes were from either Grade 5 or 6, which are the final two years of primary school in our country. For the present

study we administered the ProMAT to 467 primary school students aiming to answer the following research question:

RQ1: Which basic programming misconceptions are most prevalent in primary school children in measurements with the ProMAT?

In addition to the general prevalence of programming misconceptions in upper primary school, we are also interested in the effect that characteristics of educational programming environments might have on the formation of students' misconceptions. Based on how they represent code, educational programming environments can roughly be distinguished into text-based and block-based environments. This study is the first to comprehensively compare the prevalence of misconceptions in primary school children in a programming environment with a text-based editor (xLogo, [13]) to their prevalence in an environment with a block-based editor (Scratch [18]). To this end we developed two parallel versions of our assessment in xLogo and Scratch and aimed to address the following research question:

RQ2: Do we observe different patterns of common programming misconceptions for the two programming environments?

Building on previous work, in this study we use an assessment tool that investigates a wide range of misconceptions reported in the literature. We administered this tool to primary school students – a relatively under investigated group – and implemented the assessment in two contrasting programming environments.

2 Related Work

One way to improve programming instruction is to acquire knowledge about the concepts that students develop while learning to program. Conceptual change theories focus on the preconceptions students bring into the classroom and how these can be changed or replaced [4]. To effectively engage with this prior knowledge – especially incorrect understandings, that is misconceptions – in the classroom, they must first be identified. Similarly, models of educational reconstruction [3, 16] emphasise the importance for educators to recognise and incorporate the prior knowledge of their students. Both of these theoretical approaches underscore the relevance of investigating students' misconceptions.

Research on misconceptions in computer science education has a long history, with significant studies dating back to the 1980s. Early research by du Boulay [5] and Pea [23] describe different categories and possible sources of misconceptions. Further research documented an abundance of misconceptions programming novices might have. Over 160 of which are listed by Sorva [27]. Recently, more studies have been investigating programming misconceptions in younger learners as programming becomes part of primary education [7, 11, 19, 32, 33].

Swidan et al. [29] were the first to conduct a comprehensive assessment of programming misconceptions in children. For their study they developed a multiple-choice questionnaire with Scratch programming exercises representing a set of eleven known misconceptions, based on the misconception taxonomy of Sorva [27]. The study involved 145 participants from age 7 to 17, all of whom had some prior experience with programming. Our approach to identify relevant misconceptions is quite similar, but differs in a few key

aspects. First, we included more misconceptions that are specifically tied to four concept categories that are relevant at the primary school level, namely: sequences, loops, conditionals, and superbug (see Section 3.1 for more details). Second, we excluded variables as a category, as these are typically not taught to our target group yet. Third, we included students from Grades 5 and 6 only, working with a much more homogeneous sample and conducted our study in a typical school setting. Finally, we assessed misconceptions in two different programming environments, Scratch and xLogo, allowing us to address the question whether different programming environments lead to different patterns of misconceptions.

Educational programming environments for young learners come in various forms. Very broadly they can be divided into two categories based on the style of their editor: block-based or text-based environments. Various studies have investigated how programming environments from these two categories shape learning processes of students [e.g. 14, 30]. To the best of our knowledge, up until now only two studies have compared programming performance and understanding in primary school students across different programming environments [17, 19]. However, although these studies focused on programming understanding, neither of them has systematically assessed and compared well-defined misconceptions across two different programming environments. Lewis [17] compared two groups of students aged 10 to 12, who were learning to program in either the Scratch ($n = 26$) or in the Logo ($n = 24$) environment. The children's knowledge about loops and conditionals were assessed on the second and fifth days of the programming course, respectively. The results indicated no significant differences in knowledge about loops between the two groups. However, the Scratch learners demonstrated a better ability to interpret conditionals. Additionally, a post-course survey revealed that the Logo learners were more confident about their programming abilities.

Focusing on the understanding of loops, Mladenović et al. [19] compared the performance of 10 - 12 year-olds in Scratch ($n=46$), Logo ($n=98$), and Python ($n=63$) on five items of a multiple choice task. One item was related to sequences and the other four to increasingly difficult loop programs (simple, nested, two loops). The authors conclude that students who used Scratch exhibited fewer misconceptions related to sequences and loops, with this effect being stronger for loops in more challenging tasks. However, based on the materials and results presented in the paper we cannot deduce which specific misconceptions were found. Neither can we link them to previous misconceptions reported in the literature.

The ProMAT assessment, in which the participants have to choose between multiple-choice answers that do or do not map onto programming misconceptions, closely resembles the questionnaire of Swidan et al. [29]. This format has also been employed to investigate conceptions about the Internet [1] as well as misconceptions in other fields, such as physics [6]. The programming environments xLogo and Scratch were chosen for two reasons. First because they are frequently used in the German-speaking part of Switzerland, where this study was conducted. Second, because other studies used very similar environments for comparison [17, 19]. These choices enable us to use a quantitative assessment to investigate relevant programming misconceptions.

Figure 1: One item from both the xLogo (on the left) and the Scratch version of ProMAT. This is a translation to English - for now the test is implemented only in German.

3 Methods

3.1 The Programming Misconceptions Assessment Tool (ProMAT)

The programming misconceptions included in the ProMAT were primarily selected from the misconception inventory by Sorva [27]. Additionally, three misconceptions not covered in Sorva’s inventory were taken from more recent publications [7, 25]. From Sorva’s initial list of over 160 misconceptions, we selected those relevant to three core programming concepts typically taught at the primary school level, namely: sequences, loops, and conditionals [25]. These concepts are also part of the local curriculum. Furthermore, we included a category for misconceptions known as superbug. Misconceptions in the superbug category refer to the erroneous belief that the computer or the programming environment possesses interpretive intelligence, as first described by Pea [23]. From all misconceptions related to these four categories, we only included those with appropriate complexity for primary school students and that could be implemented in Scratch and xLogo. A few initially selected misconceptions were excluded based on findings from earlier pilot testing and post-test interviews. See Table 2 for a list of the 19 included misconceptions. During pilot testing we discovered that misconception L4 could not be assessed in the xLogo version and that misconception C4 could not be assessed in the Scratch version. We therefore removed them.

The ProMAT consists of 20 multiple-choice items, each with four answer options. The 20 items map onto the four previously described item categories, each containing five items. In each item only one answer option is correct. Typically, one or two of the remaining options are mapping onto specific misconceptions that the student might hold. See the final column in Table 2 for details on

number of misconception answers per item. Because we could not create three misconception distractors for every item, the remaining answer options are neither correct nor associated with a specific misconception and can and will therefore not be interpreted at this point. To establish internal consistency we calculated Cronbach’s Alpha and McDonald’s Omega and found acceptable values for the xLogo ProMAT ($\alpha = 0.72, \omega = 0.75$) and good values for the Scratch ProMAT ($\alpha = 0.8, \omega = 0.83$). Note that a detailed statistical validation of our assessment is the focus of a work in progress paper. All current versions of the assessment, as well as additional information on the specific items and the data sets from this study, can be accessed on our Open Science Framework project page (see appendix A).

Although we verified with the teachers that the children had been taught in either xLogo or Scratch before conducting the study, we were still mindful that this exposure might not have resulted in enough knowledge about the programming environment to have a basic understanding of the code used in the ProMAT. If individual students do not have enough understanding about the programming environment, it is unlikely that their given answers about misconceptions in this environment can be reliably interpreted. We therefore developed an additional assessment, the PreProMAT (see OSF Link for a PDF with all items). It contains items with the same type of code and concepts as in the ProMAT, but they are easier to solve and do not aim to measure specific misconceptions. The PreProMAT serves both as a warm-up, helping students engage with the test material and also as a filter for minimal familiarity of xLogo and Scratch code respectively. Concretely, we used the results from the first section (A) of the PreProMAT - assessing familiarity with the basic commands of the programming environment - to exclude

students who answered 50% or less out of the six (Scratch) or eight (xLogo) items correctly.

3.2 Versions of ProMAT

The items for the xLogo and Scratch versions of ProMAT were designed to be as parallel as possible. But to measure the same concepts in two different contexts is not trivial. In order to implement the same concepts and misconceptions in each item, some deviations were necessary due to the characteristics of the programming environments and considerations regarding what might be familiar code implementations for the students. One example of an item that needed somewhat different implementations in each programming environment can be seen in Figure 1. Both versions of the item challenge the children to closely look at the order in which the different parts of the shown program gets executed. In each instance the second answer option might indicate a misconception, in this case misconception S2 ("Subprogram code is executed according to the order in which the subprograms are defined"). These differences in the items will be taken into account in the subsequent analysis and interpretation of the results.

The ProMAT was in the final stages of development during the early data collection waves of this study (see Table 1). Most changes made were minor graphical adjustments or improvements in wording. However, five items in the xLogo version and one item in the Scratch version underwent substantial revisions. To account for these changes, data from the initial versions of these items – collected during waves 1 and 2 – were excluded from the analysis. Only data from the revised versions of these six items, collected during waves 3 and 4, were retained. This approach allows us to treat the two data collection waves for each version of ProMAT – Scratch and xLogo – as a single sample for analysis.

3.3 Procedure

Approval for this study was obtained from the Ethics Committee of ETH Zurich (case number: EK-2021-N-82). Teachers of Grades 5 and 6, whose classes had prior programming experience with either Scratch or xLogo, were contacted. These teachers were approached through various channels, including a collaborating project school, previous participation in programming interventions, and through teachers involved in a programming challenge with their classes. All students completed both the PreProMAT and the ProMAT in their respective classrooms using their own digital devices, either laptops or tablets. The first author was present during the assessment to ensure that all participants completed the test within a single school lesson (45 minutes). This study encompasses four different data collection waves, two each for the Scratch and xLogo environments. See Table 1 for a detailed time frame of the different data collection waves. Some data collection waves included post-test interviews with selected students (wave 1) or additional cognitive tests after the ProMAT (waves 2 and 3). However, these supplementary data will not be analyzed in this study.

3.4 Participants

The participants in this study were students from Grades 5 and 6 (ages 10–13) attending primary schools in German-speaking Switzerland. This age range was chosen because programming becomes

part of the curriculum at this stage in this region [2]. All students had prior programming experience from school lessons with either the xLogo or Scratch programming environments and were given the ProMAT test version corresponding to their familiar environment. In case of the Scratch group, all classes were taught by the teachers themselves. The classes in the xLogo group on the other hand, had had external experts visit and teach at least ten computer science lessons.

From the total 467 children that participated, we excluded 101 based on their results in the PreProMAT ($n = 89$ for Scratch and $n = 12$ for xLogo and), which left 366 children (176 girls) for data analysis - see section 3.1 for the exclusion criterion. Of the remaining participants, 114 were in Grade 5 and 252 in Grade 6, with 111 students completing the xLogo version and 255 students completing the Scratch version (see Table 1). Overall, we recruited more Grade 6 than Grade 5 classes and more classes with experience in the Scratch than in the xLogo environment to participate in our study - this is reflected in the sample. However, proportionally more children from the Scratch than from the xLogo group had to be excluded due to insufficient understanding of their programming environment.

4 Results

Figure 2 illustrates the prevalence of all investigated misconceptions for both the Scratch and xLogo data sets. Each bar chart consists of three parts:

- (1) **Misconception Answers:** On the left side, the orange bars show the percentage of students who selected answers that might indicate a specific misconception. A higher percentage means that more students chose this answer, suggesting the misconception is more widespread.
- (2) **Correct Answers:** Next, the blue bars represent the percentage of students who chose the correct answer for items related to that specific misconception. Contrasting the prevalence of misconceptions with the students' understanding of the correct concepts.
- (3) **Other Distractor Answers:** The remaining section of each bar chart shows the percentage of students who selected other distractor answers not associated with any known misconception.

For misconceptions that appeared in multiple ProMAT items (see the rightmost column in Table 2), Figure 2 displays the average percentages for both the misconception-related answers and the correct answers across these items.

4.1 Within programming environment comparisons

L5 and L6, both related to the loops concept, are the most prevalent misconceptions in the Scratch environment, with over 40% of students selecting answers indicating these misconceptions in the corresponding ProMAT items (for specific values, refer to Figure 2). Other prevalent misconceptions are C3 from the conditionals category, as well as S3 and S2 from the sequences category. Most misconceptions from the superbug category have low percentages, indicating they are likely not very prevalent. The superbug category also shows the highest rates of correct answers.

Table 1: Overview of the samples from the four data collection waves used in this study. The numbers shown represent the sample after participants scoring low in the PreProMAT were excluded.

	data collection wave			
	1 - xLogo	2 - xLogo	3 - Scratch	4 - Scratch
time	March - May 2022	July 2022	November 2022	April - July 2023
sample size	n = 64	n = 47	n = 67	n = 188
sample by grade	n grade 5 = 32	n grade 5 = 28	n grade 5 = 0	n grade 5 = 54
	n grade 6 = 32	n grade 6 = 19	n grade 6 = 67	n grade 6 = 134
sample by gender	n female = 30	n female = 19	n female = 28	n female = 99
	n male = 34	n male = 27	n male = 39	n male = 86

For xLogo the top three misconceptions are in three different concept categories: misconception S2 from the sequences category, misconception C3 from the conditionals category, and misconception SB4 from the superbug category (see Figure 2). The highest prevalence was found for misconception S2, with over 50% of students choosing answers linked to this misconception over alternatives. In total, six misconceptions have values over 20%, the last of which is misconception L1, the highest misconception from the loops category. Besides L1, the prevalence values for the other misconceptions in the loops category are relatively low.

4.2 Between programming environment comparisons

Table 3 presents the averaged percentage values of all misconceptions across their respective categories. While these values may not be very meaningful on their own, they provide an overall ranking of categories based on the prevalence of misconceptions for each data set. The results show that the rankings differ between Scratch and xLogo. In the Scratch data, the loops category has the highest average prevalence, while the superbug category has the lowest. In contrast, in the xLogo data, the sequences category has the highest prevalence, and the loops category has the lowest. Note that the standard deviations are rather large in some cases, so the specific order should not be overly emphasized and it is more meaningful to look at the separate misconceptions within the categories.

For example, for sequence-related misconceptions we observe varying patterns in prevalence values between the two programming environments. For Scratch, the prevalence of all three misconceptions ranged rather consistently from 12-18%. In contrast, in the xLogo environment, misconceptions S1 and S3 had low prevalence rates around 8%, while misconception S2 showed the highest prevalence overall in the xLogo data.

Another observation within the loop concept category for both programming environments is the result pattern across misconception L1 ("Adjacent code executes within loop") and its two variations, L2 ("only code after the loop is also executed") and L3 ("code before and after the loop is also executed"). In both the Scratch and the xLogo version, misconception L3 is consistently chosen less often than L2, indicating that students are more likely to wrongly include code after a loop as if it were within the loop, rather than wrongly including code before the loop.

5 Discussion

5.1 The most prevalent misconceptions

The objective of this study was to investigate the programming misconceptions that primary school children show when they begin learning to program. RQ1 specifically stated: Which basic programming misconceptions are most prevalent in primary school children in measurements with the ProMAT?

For Scratch, we found these five misconceptions to be the most prevalent:

- (1) L6: Students articulated that a loop repeats the same set of actions and expected loops to produce the exact same output in every iteration.
- (2) L5: When there are multiple actions inside a loop, instead of executing a sequence of actions in a loop and then repeating the entire sequence, some students tend to repeat each action separately before repeating the subsequent action(s), thus grouping the actions in the loop.
- (3) C3: The THEN branch is always executed.
- (4) S2: Subprogram code is executed according to the order in which the subprograms are defined.
- (5) S3: The sequence of commands does not matter.

Among these five highest-ranking misconceptions for the Scratch environment, two are related to the loops category and two to the sequences category, which also show the highest average prevalence rates (see Table 3). From the conditionals category, one high ranking misconception (C3) stands out, while other misconceptions from both the conditionals and superbug categories show low prevalence rates.

For xLogo, we found these five misconceptions to be the most prevalent:

- (1) S2: Subprogram code is executed according to the order in which the subprograms are defined.
- (2) C3: The THEN branch is always executed.
- (3) SB4: The machine understands English / language of user
- (4) C2: A false condition ends program if no ELSE branch.
- (5) L1: Adjacent code executes within loop.

In contrast to Scratch, the top five misconceptions for xLogo came from all four concept categories. Misconception S2 stands out with a very high value. However, the other two misconceptions from the sequences category are near the bottom of the list, suggesting that difficulties with sequences in xLogo are specifically related to subprogram code execution order. Similarly, only misconception L1 from the loops category shows a high prevalence, while the

Table 2: Misconceptions included in the ProMAT and their respective concept categories are shown. The last column indicates in how many items the specific misconception appears as an answer option - separately for the Scratch and xLogo versions of the assessment.

Number	Misconception Description	Category	Items per Misconception (Scratch / xLogo)
S1	Magical parallelism: several lines of a (simple non-concurrent) program can be simultaneously active or known.	Sequences	3 / 2
S2	Subprogram code is executed according to the order in which the subprograms are defined.	Sequences	2 / 2
S3	The sequence of commands does not matter.	Sequences	1 / 1
L1	Adjacent code executes within loop.	Loops	2 / 2
L2	Code after the loop executes within loop.	Loops	1 / 1
L3	Code before and after the loop executes within loop.	Loops	1 / 1
L4	WHILE loops terminate as soon as condition changes to false.	Loops	1 / 0
L5	When there are multiple actions inside a loop, instead of executing a sequence of actions in a loop and then repeating the entire sequence, some students tend to repeat each action separately before repeating the subsequent action(s), thus grouping the actions in the loop.	Loops	1 / 2
L6	Students articulated that a loop repeats the same set of actions and expected loops to produce the exact same output in every iteration.	Loops	1 / 2
C1	Code after IF statement is not executed if the THEN clause is.	Conditionals	3 / 1
C2	A false condition ends program if no ELSE branch.	Conditionals	1 / 2
C3	The THEN branch is always executed.	Conditionals	3 / 4
C4	Control goes back to start when condition is false.	Conditionals	0 / 1
C5	Values of conditional expressions get printed out.	Conditionals	1 / 1
SB1	The computer knows the intention of the program or of a piece of code (or the programmer), and acts accordingly.	Superbug	3 / 4
SB2	Values are updated automatically according to a logical context.	Superbug	1 / 1
SB3	The system does not allow unreasonable operations.	Superbug	2 / 3
SB4	The machine understands English [language of User/Environment]	Superbug	2 / 2
SB5	The natural-language semantics of variable names affects which value gets assigned to which variable.	Superbug	1 / 1

other misconceptions are less common. The misconception C3 from the conditionals category ranked very high. However, the interpretation of this finding is not straightforward and we will come back to this in the Limitations section.

When comparing our findings to those of Swidan et al. [29], we observe some notable similarities and differences. The most

frequently reported misconception in their study was misconception 23 from the list by Sorva [27]: "Difficulties in understanding the sequentiality of statements." In our assessment, this misconception was not directly included, since it is representative of all three included misconceptions in the sequences category. Of these misconceptions, S2 and S3 were in the top five for the Scratch data and S2 was the most frequent misconception for xLogo. Thus we

Figure 2: Results on the ProMAT in Scratch (left) and xLogo (right), grouped by category and ordered by misconception prevalence. Each horizontal bar represents the percentage of selected answers corresponding to a misconception (orange), the correct answer (blue) and remaining distractors (grey).

have some indication that our results for the sequences category are broadly in line with the data from Swidan and colleagues and

also highlights the importance of the sequences category. As in our study, Swidan and colleagues included several misconceptions

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of misconception prevalence were averaged across their respective categories for both ProMAT versions. The relative rank of each category, based on the highest average prevalence, is also shown.

category	Scratch			xLogo		
	rank	mean %	SD %	rank	mean %	SD %
Sequences	2	16.4	3.1	1	23.2	25.9
Loops	1	19.6	17.9	4	11.9	8.3
Conditionals	3	12.6	9.8	2	21.0	16.5
Superbug	4	8.5	4.6	3	18.4	6.9

about control structures. Notably, misconception L1, which was fourth in their ranking, also had a high prevalence in our xLogo data. Interestingly, this misconception seemed less problematic in our Scratch data - the same programming environment the study from Swidan and colleagues used. Looking closely at specific items in their questionnaire and the ProMAT, we can see, that their item includes a variable and ours does not. Grover and Basu [7] reported in their study that participating middle school children struggled with variables, which might explain why Swidan et al. [29] found a higher prevalence of misconceptions. Misconception C2 on the other hand ranked low in both their and our Scratch data. Here the corresponding items and the misconception answer options across both assessments are very similar - providing some evidence for criterion validity for our assessment. Additionally, the other two loops- and conditionals-related misconceptions examined in both studies, misconceptions C4 and L4, ranked relatively low in both our studies. Thus, overall, when we take into account the differences in item design such as the addition of variables, our findings for the Scratch data seem to reasonably align with those of Swidan and colleagues.

Grover and Basu [7], who investigated misconceptions of loops, variables, and boolean logic in Grade 6-8 children in Scratch, were the first to report misconception L5. While L5 showed a very high prevalence in our Scratch sample, it was reported by only a minority of participants in Grover and Basu [7]'s study. This difference in prevalence is probably due to the fact that Grover and Basu [7] discovered the L5 misconception during the interviews they held with their participants, while we systematically assessed it with a multiple choice test. Another reason may be the higher age of the participants in their study.

5.2 Differences in misconception patterns between the two programming environments

To answer RQ 2 (Do we observe different patterns of common programming misconceptions for the two programming environments?), we compared the results from the two environments across the four categories of misconceptions: sequences, loops, conditionals, and superbug. The averaged prevalence of all the misconceptions from each category can be seen in Table 3. While there is an overall difference in the prevalence of misconceptions answers between xLogo (18.6 %) and Scratch(14.3%), it should be noted, that direct comparisons of percentages between these programming

environments is not straightforward and we will therefore focus on differences in programming misconception patterns within the four categories instead. In addition, we will try to connect these to specific features of the programming environments and the programming experiences of the children.

The marked difference in the loops category across the two programming environments is mostly attributable to two misconceptions, L5 and L6, which appear much more frequently in the Scratch test versions. Both of these misconceptions relate to specific step-by-step behaviour of simple loop structures. One possible explanation for this discrepancy is that the design and instructional focus of xLogo facilitate a better understanding of the behaviour of loops within the specific programming environment than the Scratch environment does. If we consider these two programming environments as representative for environments with text-based (xLogo) and block-based (Scratch) editors, these findings appear at first glance to go against the notion that block-based environments facilitate the understanding of code structures for students, as is sometimes argued [8]. However, a closer look at the specific misconceptions can explain these observations. Namely, one method employed by Scratch (and other block-based programming environments) to facilitate comprehension of loop structures is the use of a c-shaped bracket block that encompasses all code within a loop, in contrast to the typed brackets utilized text-based environments like xLogo (see Figure 3). An objective of this c-shaped block is to facilitate the differentiation between code within and outside the loop structure. In our results, we found that the misconception L1, which concerns this differentiation, appeared more frequently in xLogo than in Scratch. This could suggest that the design features of Scratch, and potentially those of block-based programming environments more generally, facilitate the reduction of some misconceptions regarding loops, such as misconception L1, but not others, such as misconceptions L5 and L6. Which converges with the results from Weintrop and Wilensky [31], who also found fewer errors concerned with the scope of loops in block-based environments. As mentioned, both L5 and L6 are concerned with the inner workings of loops and it seems reasonable that the visualisation of the boundaries of a loop that a c-shaped block provides, might not help with these specific misconceptions.

Figure 3: An example of the same simple loop structure implemented in the educational programming environments Scratch (on the left) and xLogo.

Of particular interest within the sequences category is misconception S2. This misconception, related to the order of subprogram

code, was frequently observed in both test environments, but occurred much more frequently in xLogo. The higher prevalence of this misconception in xLogo suggests that students found it challenging to use functions correctly when they were not presented in the correct order. In contrast, students who used Scratch appeared to be more accustomed to changing the order in which functions are called. This could be attributed to a design feature of Scratch, which enables users to position code components at will within the code area. In contrast, the xLogo interface offers a more traditional and linear scripting area.

Misconception S3 ("The sequence of commands does not matter") appears prominently in the Scratch data but ranks low for xLogo. This difference might be attributed to the nature of drawing with the turtle in xLogo versus moving sprites in Scratch. When students experiment with drawing shapes in xLogo, they quickly realize that exact sequencing is crucial – even for details like whether to execute a turn command or a move command first. Conversely, in Scratch, it is more common for students to reposition sprites and restart a single program multiple times. In Scratch, sprites typically do not draw lines, making it less obvious what the exact sequence was that led to a specific state. These differences in interaction with the programming environment likely contribute to the varying prevalence of misconception S3 between Scratch and xLogo.

The superbug category showed a higher prevalence of misconceptions in the xLogo data compared to Scratch. At this point we do not have an explanation for this difference. But generally, it is worth noting that there is considerable conceptual overlap between some of the misconceptions in this category, namely SB1, SB2, SB3, and SB4. These four misconceptions involve erroneous beliefs about the computer's understanding of either the programmer, natural language, or logic. These misconceptions manifest very similarly in practical programming and also in our test items, making it difficult to distinguish between them. This similarity is also reflected in the relatively low standard deviations of misconception values in this category for both assessment versions - Scratch SD = 4.6% and xLogo SD = 6.9 % (see Table 3).

Misconception answers in the conditionals category appeared more frequently for the xLogo than for the Scratch environment, and the related items were less often solved correctly. This makes sense, considering that conditionals are introduced late in the official teaching materials for xLogo [12] and are often skipped by teachers. Additionally, one could argue that conditionals are not particularly useful for drawing intricate shapes, which is a typical beginner exercise in xLogo. Consequently, many students that are using xLogo are less familiar with conditionals. We therefore think that children might have relied more on heuristics or guessing when faced with conditionals-related questions, which increases the chance that their incorrect answers might not indicate a misconception. We were aware of this during testing but chose to include the conditionals items anyway instead of having no data at all for this concept. In addition, the answers to these items might become more reliable after children have received targeted instructions about conditionals in xLogo. We are therefore reluctant to remove this category from the xLogo version of the ProMAT. However, for the current study we must interpret the results of the conditionals category for the xLogo data with caution.

Just like Lewis [17] we found that students in the Scratch environment exhibited fewer misconceptions in the conditionals category compared to xLogo. However, as previously discussed, our findings for the conditionals category in xLogo need to be interpreted with caution. However, in contrast to Lewis and Mladenović et al. [19], we found that our Scratch learners displayed more misconceptions about loops than xLogo learners. One reason for this discrepancy could be differences in study design. In Lewis's study, students were required to formulate written answers to each item. This more language-focused approach, along with the small sample size, might have obscured potential differences between the two programming environments. Another factor, that could also explain the differences with the results of Mladenović and colleagues, could be differences in the visual presentation of the items. While both Lewis [17] and Mladenović et al. [19] only showed the blank code for the Logo items, we included a picture of the xLogo programming environment with each item, which features, among other elements, colours for different code features (see Fig 1 for reference). Presenting xLogo students with tasks featuring code that closely resembled their familiar programming environment and including some structuring features, might have helped them to better understand the loop structures. In addition, we used a variety of blocks in the loop items in the Scratch version of ProMAT, whereas Mladenović and colleagues used the same commands inside all their loop items. This might have made our items in Scratch somewhat more difficult than theirs. These considerations suggest that differences in visual presentation, item design, and study methodology could account for the discrepancies in findings regarding loop misconceptions between our study and those of Lewis [17] and Mladenović et al. [19], as well as the investigations from Swidan et al. [29] and Grover and Basu [7] which we discussed previously in section 5.1. It highlights the importance considering seemingly small details when comparing studies in this field, as absolute prevalence values appear to be highly context-dependent.

5.3 Limitations

The first limitation of this study, as with any questionnaire investigation, is that selecting a specific answer option does not necessarily indicate that a student holds that misconception in their mind. A particular answer could be chosen due to a reasoning process based on a firmly held misconception or because the student, maybe being uncertain, employed a heuristic. Such heuristics were sometimes reported during earlier pilot testing where some children reported, that they focused on the parts of the shown program they were most familiar with and ignored other parts. Because it is hard to eliminate these uncertainties with quantitative tests, we must interpret answer percentages, like the ones reported here, not as definite indicators but as general guides for further investigation. Here this is particularly relevant for the conditionals category in the xLogo environment.

Secondly, and related to the first point, we must also exercise caution when comparing results from the two different programming environments. Even within a single programming environment, creating parallel items is challenging, and seemingly minor changes can lead to significant differences in difficulty [22]. In other words,

assessing the same programming misconceptions in different programming environments using different representations is very hard, if not almost impossible. Therefore, we focused on the relative differences between concept categories and misconceptions and discussed possible causes based on features of the environments, without directly comparing test performance or misconception percentages.

A third limitation were the varying levels of prior programming knowledge of the participants. Despite the fact that the children were recruited from a narrow age range and that they all had received programming lessons at school prior to the data collection, and we even excluded children who did not show enough knowledge on the PreProMAT, there was still considerable variation in their experience, the number of lessons, and the exact topics covered varied across classes. Some students may have missed some of the lessons. While others may have been engaged in programming activities outside of school, and may even be familiar with other programming environments. These factors are unavoidable when measuring student data in a regular school setting. As stated, we tried to at least partly target this problem by excluding students who scored low on the PreProMAT. From this we observed, that proportionally more students from the Scratch group had to be excluded. To further minimise such exclusions or differences in the future, we would need to conduct a training study in which both the xLogo and Scratch groups receive a set amount of standardised lessons before taking the ProMAT and would need to control for programming experience outside of the school. However, the results of such a study would not have high ecological validity because the amount and type of programming instructions is simply still highly variable in schools.

A fourth limitation is the regional and programming environment scope of the study. All data was collected in German-speaking Switzerland, with students following the national curriculum [2]. Educational curricula and traditions vary significantly across countries, and we might have observed other prevalence of misconceptions if data had been collected from other regions or by using different educational programming environments.

5.4 Conclusions

This study aimed to investigate the programming misconceptions that primary school students might form when they begin learning to program. Using the ProMAT assessment tool in both Scratch and xLogo environments, we identified several prevalent misconceptions. In Scratch, some misconceptions related to loops were most common, in particular the belief that loops produce the exact same output in every iteration (L6) and that each command inside a loop is repeated separately (L5). In xLogo, misconceptions about the order of subprogram execution (S2) and the computer's interpretive intelligence (SB4) were particularly frequent.

Our comparison with the findings of Swidan et al. [29] revealed both similarities and differences in programming misconceptions among young learners. While our study confirmed some of their results, it also identified unique misconceptions specific to the programming environments used. Building on their findings, we highlighted relevant aspects that warrant further research, such

as the influence of environment-specific design features on the formation of misconceptions.

The differences observed between the two programming environments, xLogo and Scratch, suggest that the design and instructional focus of each can influence the formation of certain misconceptions. These findings underscore the importance of considering environment-specific factors when designing educational interventions to address programming misconceptions.

Overall, this study contributes to our understanding of which misconceptions primary school students might form and how those misconceptions might differ between programming environments. It also highlights the need for targeted teaching strategies to mitigate misconceptions, ensuring a more robust foundation in programming education for young learners.

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References

- [1] Parvaneh Babari, Michael Hielscher, Peter Adriaan Edelsbrunner, Beat Döbeli Honegger, Bettina Waldvogel, and Eva Marinus. 2023. Using Concept Cartoons for Assessing Children's Conceptions about the Internet. In *Proceedings of the 18th WiPSCe Conference on Primary and Secondary Computing Education Research*. ACM, Cambridge United Kingdom, 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3605468.3605496>
- [2] Deutschschweizer Erziehungsdirektoren-Konferenz. 2015. Schlussbericht der Arbeitsgruppe zu Medien und Informatik im Lehrplan 21.
- [3] Ira Diethelm, Peter Hubwieser, and Robert Klaus. 2012. Students, teachers and phenomena: educational reconstruction for computer science education. In *Proceedings of the 12th Koli Calling International Conference on Computing Education Research (Koli Calling '12)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 164–173. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2401796.2401823> event-place: Koli, Finland.
- [4] Andrea A. DiSessa. 2014. A history of conceptual change research: Threads and fault lines. *The Cambridge Handbook of the Learning Sciences, Second Edition* 99, 3 (2014), 88–108. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139519526.007> ISBN: 9781139519526.
- [5] Benedict du Boulay. 1986. Some Difficulties of Learning to Program. *Journal of Educational Computing Research* 2, 1 (Feb. 1986), 57–73. <https://doi.org/10.2190/3LFX-9RRF-67T8-UVK9>
- [6] Peter A. Edelsbrunner, Lennart Schalk, Ralph Schumacher, and Elsbeth Stern. 2018. Variable control and conceptual change: A large-scale quantitative study in elementary school. *Learning and Individual Differences* 66, February (2018), 38–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2018.02.003> Publisher: Elsevier.
- [7] Shuchi Grover and Satabdi Basu. 2017. Measuring student learning in introductory block-based programming: Examining misconceptions of loops, variables, and Boolean logic. In *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM SIGCSE Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education (SIGCSE '17)*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 267–272. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3017680.3017723> ISBN: 9781450346986.
- [8] Shuchi Grover and Roy Pea. 2013. Computational Thinking in K–12: A Review of the State of the Field. *Educational Researcher* 42, 1 (Jan. 2013), 38–43. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X12463051>
- [9] Nurjailam Hamzah, Siti Mistima Maat, and Zanaton Ikhsan. 2021. A systematic review on pupils' misconceptions and errors in trigonometry. *Pegegog Journal of Education and Instruction* 11, 4 (Oct. 2021), 209–218. <https://doi.org/10.47750/pegegog.11.04.20>
- [10] Marco Hartmann, Peter Edelsbrunner, Michael Hielscher, Giulia Paparo, Beat Döbeli Honegger, and Eva Marinus. 2022. Programming concepts and misconceptions in grade 5 and 6 children: Developing and testing a new assessment tool. In *Atti del 5° Convegno sulle didattiche disciplinari*. Dipartimento formazione e apprendimento – SUPSI, Svizzera / swissuniversities, Svizzera, 328–333. <https://doi.org/10.33683/dida.22.05.59>
- [11] Felienne Hermans, Alaaeddin Swidan, Efthimia Aivaloglou, and Marileen Smit. 2018. Thinking out of the Box: Comparing metaphors for variables in programming education. In *Proceedings of the 13th Workshop in Primary and Secondary Computing Education (WiPSCe '18)*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3265757.3265765> ISBN: 9781450365888.

- [12] Juraj Hromkovič and Tobias Kohn. 2018. *Einfach informatik*. Ernst Klett Verlag.
- [13] Juraj Hromkovič, Giovanni Serafini, and Jacqueline Staub. 2017. XLogoOnline: A single-page, browser-based programming environment for schools aiming at reducing cognitive load on pupils. In *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, Vol. 10696 LNCS. Springer International Publishing, 219–231. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-71483-7_18 ISSN: 16113349.
- [14] Yue Hu, Cheng Huan Chen, and Chien Yuan Su. 2021. Exploring the Effectiveness and Moderators of Block-Based Visual Programming on Student Learning: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Educational Computing Research* 58, 8 (2021), 1467–1493. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0735633120945935>
- [15] Uffe Thomas Jankvist and Mogens Niss. 2018. Counteracting Destructive Student Misconceptions of Mathematics. *Education Sciences* 8, 2 (April 2018), 53. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci8020053>
- [16] Ulrich Kattmann, Reinders Duit, Harald GROPENGEßER, and Michael Komorek. 1996. Educational reconstruction—bringing together issues of scientific clarification and students’ conceptions. In *Annual meeting of the national association of research in science teaching (NARST)*, St. Louis. 1–20.
- [17] Colleen M. Lewis. 2010. How programming environment shapes perception, learning and goals: Logo vs. Scratch. In *SIGCSE’10 - Proceedings of the 41st ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education*. 346–350. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1734263.1734383> ISBN: 9781605588858.
- [18] John Maloney, Mitchel Resnick, Natalie Rusk, Brian Silverman, and Evelyn Eastmond. 2010. The Scratch Programming Language and Environment. *ACM Transactions on Computing Education* 10, 4 (Nov. 2010), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1868358.1868363>
- [19] Monika Mladenović, Ivica Boljat, and Žana Žanko. 2017. Comparing loops misconceptions in block-based and text-based programming languages at the K-12 level. *Education and Information Technologies* 23, 4 (2017), 1483–1500. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-017-9673-3>
- [20] Christin Nenner and Nadine Bergner. 2022. Informatics Education in German Primary School Curricula. In *Informatics in Schools. A Step Beyond Digital Education*, Andreas Bollin and Gerald Futschek (Eds.). Springer International Publishing, Cham, 3–14.
- [21] UK Department of Education. 2013. National curriculum in England: computing programmes of study. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-curriculum-in-england-computing-programmes-of-study>
- [22] Miranda C. Parker, Leiny Garcia, Yvonne S. Kao, Diana Franklin, Susan Krause, and Mark Warschauer. 2022. A Pair of ACES: An Analysis of Isomorphic Questions on an Elementary Computing Assessment. In *Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research - Volume 1*. ACM, Lugano and Virtual Event Switzerland, 2–14. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3501385.3543979>
- [23] Roy D. Pea. 1986. Language-independent conceptual “bugs” in novice programming. *Journal of Educational Computing Research* 2, 1 (1986), 25–36.
- [24] Yizhou Qian and James Lehman. 2017. Students’ Misconceptions and Other Difficulties in Introductory Programming. *ACM Transactions on Computing Education* 18, 1 (Dec. 2017), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3077618>
- [25] Kathryn M. Rich, Carla Strickland, T. Andrew Binkowski, Cheryl Moran, and Diana Franklin. 2017. K-8 Learning Trajectories Derived from Research Literature: Sequence, Repetition, Conditionals. In *Proceedings of the 2017 ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research*, Vol. 9. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 182–190. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3105726.3106166> Issue: 1 ISSN: 21532192.
- [26] Philip M. Sadler, Gerhard Sonnert, Harold P. Coyle, Nancy Cook-Smith, and Jaimie L. Miller. 2013. The Influence of Teachers’ Knowledge on Student Learning in Middle School Physical Science Classrooms. *American Educational Research Journal* 50, 5 (Oct. 2013), 1020–1049. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831213477680>
- [27] Juha Sorva. 2012. *Visual Program Simulation in Introductory Program Education*. Ph. D. Dissertation. Aalto University.
- [28] Juha Sorva. 2013. Notional machines and introductory programming education. In *ACM Transactions on Computing Education*, Vol. 13. 31. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2483710.2483713>
- [29] Alaaeddin Swidan, Feliene Hermans, and Marileen Smit. 2018. Programming misconceptions for school students. In *ICER 2018 - Proceedings of the 2018 ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research*. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 151–159. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3230977.3230995> ISBN: 9781450356282.
- [30] David Weintrop, Heather Killen, and Baker Franke. 2018. Blocks or Text? How Programming Language Modality Makes a Difference in Assessing Underrepresented Populations. *International Society of the Learning Sciences*, 328–335.
- [31] David Weintrop and Uri Wilensky. 2015. Using commutative assessments to compare conceptual understanding in blocks-based and text-based programs. In *ICER 2015 - Proceedings of the 2015 ACM Conference on International Computing Education Research*. 101–110. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2787622.2787721> ISBN: 9781450336284.
- [32] Žana Žanko, Monika Mladenović, and Ivica Boljat. 2019. Misconceptions about variables at the K-12 level. *Education and Information Technologies* 24, 2 (2019), 1251–1268. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-018-9824-1> ISBN: 1063901898.
- [33] Žana Žanko, Monika Mladenović, and Divna Krpan. 2023. Mediated transfer: impact on programming misconceptions. *Journal of Computers in Education* 10, 0123456789 (2023), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-022-00225-z> Publisher: Springer Berlin Heidelberg ISBN: 4069202200225.

A Online Resources

All datasets and annotated test versions of ProMAT can be accessed via this link to our Open Science Framework project: https://osf.io/5bvxpv/?view_only=d6a51b4cfd4e63887fde5da9ef66c7

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